

FLIPPED CLASSROOM MODEL. ANALYZE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE FLIPPED CLASSROOM APPROACH COMPARED TO TRADITIONAL TEACHING METHODS IN VARIOUS SUBJECTS OR GRADE LEVELS

Bustonova Shahloxon Bahriddin qizi

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institution, student

Qurbonova Yulduz Umarovna

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institution, English teacher

Annotation: Education refers to the systematic process of acquiring knowledge, skills, values, and competencies through various forms of instruction, training, and experiences. It is lifelong journey that encompasses formal, informal, and non-formal learning environments. Structured, classroom-based learning provided by trained educators, typically leading to certifications or degrees. Just as no other traditional learning styles are identical, such is the case with flipped learning. Flipped learning classroom methodology is an educational approach that reverses the traditional learning environment by delivering instructional content outside of the classroom and engaging students in activities during class time. This article will shed lights on full and precise description suitable for flipped learning methodology.

Key words: passive learning, pre-class learning, in-class activities, flexible learning pace, enhanced teacher-student interaction, use of technology, active learning, personalized learning, collaborative environment.

At the front of the room, a teacher is engaged in explaining the Civil War, utilizing a whiteboard for notes. The students, seated in orderly rows, diligently jot down notes. When the class concludes, they're assigned to read certain sections from a dense textbook and to complete the chapter's questions for homework. This pivotal, yet unresolved era of American history has been condensed into a routine and somewhat uninspiring task. The teacher realizes that the lesson's core messages haven't been grasped by all, yet the constraints of the 50-minute session leave no room for individual clarification. The following day, homework will be collected and quickly checked, but lingering on additional queries is not an option due to the tight timetable and the vast syllabus awaiting before the unit's final assessment.

Teachers are actively moving away from traditional lecture-based teaching methods, focusing instead on tailoring instruction to meet the unique learning needs

of each student. This shift has led to the adoption of the Flipped Learning model, where digital tools are employed to transfer direct teaching to the individual's space, often through video content. This rearrangement of instructional time enables educators to spend more personal time with students. As a result, there's increased opportunity for students to work together on projects, delve deeper into the material, refine their skills, and get personalized feedback. Consequently, educators can invest more effort into mentoring their students, fostering their skill development, and guiding them through more complex projects that enhance their autonomy in learning.

Considered pioneers of Flipped Learning, two chemistry teachers from rural Colorado launched this approach in 2007. They were concerned about students often missing end-of-day classes due to traveling to other schools for competitions, games, or events. To address this, they started using live video recordings and screencasting software to capture lectures, demonstrations, and annotated slide presentations. These resources were uploaded to the then-emerging platform YouTube, enabling students to download and access them at their convenience. However, the delivery method proved less significant than the opportunities it provided. In their 2012 book, "Flip Your Classroom: Reach Every Student in Every Class Every Day," authors Jonathan Bergmann and Aaron Sams revealed that flipping the classroom led to increased student interaction during lessons. Additionally, the flexible use of class time allowed for more personalized support for struggling students, while advanced learners could continue to advance their knowledge.

In early 2012, Sams and Bergmann started the not-for-profit Flipped Learning Network™ (FLN) to provide

educators with the knowledge, skills, and resources to successfully implement the Flipped Learning model.

The goals of the organization are to provide professional learning opportunities on Flipped Learning; to

conduct, collaborate and disseminate relevant research on Flipped Learning; and to act as the clearinghouse for distributing best/promising practices for current and future “flipped” educators. One gauge to measure the interest in flipped Learning is indicated by the number of participants in the Ning; in January 2012, there were 2,500 members; by March 2013, more than 12,000 educators had signed up.

Traditional teaching often centers around lectures where the teacher imparts knowledge while students passively listen and take notes. This passive approach can lead to disengagement and a lack of retention of information since learners are not

actively involved in the learning process. In a conventional classroom setting, teachers often have large groups of students, making it challenging to provide individualized attention and support. As a result, students who struggle may fall behind without the necessary guidance.

One-Size-Fits-All Approach: Traditional methods typically follow a standard curriculum that does not account for the diverse learning styles and paces of students. This can lead to some students feeling overwhelmed while others find the material unchallenging.

Traditional teaching often prioritizes rote memorization of facts and information over practical application. This can result in students being ill-prepared to apply their knowledge in real-world situations and job settings.

Conventional classrooms often emphasize individual work over collaboration. This can stifle communication and teamwork skills, which are crucial in today's collaborative work environments.

Traditional education can discourage creative thinking and exploration. With strict adherence to curricula and standardized testing, students may fear taking risks or thinking outside the box, which are essential for innovation.

The flipped classroom methodology is an innovative instructional strategy that reverses the traditional learning environment. Instead of the typical format where a teacher provides direct instruction during class time and assigns homework for practice, the flipped classroom model allows students to learn new content at home and then engage in hands-on activities and discussions in class. Here's how it works:

Key Components of the Flipped Classroom Model:

1. Pre-Class Learning:

- Students are assigned instructional materials (like video lectures, readings, or online modules) to study at home. This can include watching recorded lectures, reading articles, or exploring interactive content.
- The focus is on having students acquire foundational knowledge before entering the classroom.

2. In-Class Activities:

- Class time is dedicated to interactive learning experiences. Teachers facilitate activities that promote engagement, collaboration, and application of knowledge, such as group discussions, problem-solving tasks, or hands-on projects.
- This active learning environment fosters deeper understanding and helps students apply what they've learned.

3. Flexible Learning Pace:

- Students have the flexibility to learn at their own pace. They can pause, rewind, and re-watch instructional materials as needed, which accommodates diverse learning styles and needs.

4. Enhanced Teacher-Student Interaction:

- With less time spent on direct instruction, teachers can focus more on supporting individual students, providing feedback, and facilitating discussions.

- Teachers can assess students' understanding in real-time and adjust their instructional strategies accordingly.

5. Use of Technology:

- The flipped classroom often incorporates various technologies like video platforms, learning management systems (LMS), and digital resources to deliver content and facilitate communication.

Benefits of the Flipped Classroom Methodology:

- Active Learning: Students become more active participants in their learning, leading to better engagement and retention of knowledge.

- Personalized Learning: Students can control their learning experience, allowing them to spend more time on challenging concepts.

- Collaborative Environment: Classroom time becomes an opportunity for collaboration, discussion, and peer-to-peer learning.

- Immediate Feedback: Teachers can provide real-time feedback and guidance during class, helping students overcome learning obstacles.

Challenges to Consider:

- Access to Technology: Not all students may have access to the necessary technology or internet at home.

- Preparation: Instructors need to invest time in creating high-quality instructional materials.

- Student Accountability: Ensuring that students come prepared to class can be challenging.

The flipped classroom methodology reshapes how educators approach teaching and learning, fostering a more dynamic and interactive classroom environment.

DEFINING THE FLIPPED LEARNING:

In the Flipped Learning model, teachers transition direct instruction from the large group setting to individual learning environments, utilizing various technologies. They create screencasts that narrate their work on computer desktops, record videos of their teaching, or curate lessons from online platforms like TED-Ed and Khan Academy. In the traditional teacher-centered model, the teacher is the main

source of information, the teacher is the “sage on the stage” (King, 1993), i.e. the sole content expert who provides information to students, generally via direct instruction lecture. In the Flipped Learning model, there is a deliberate shift from a teacher-centered classroom to a student centered approach, where in-class time is meant for exploring topics in greater depth and creating richer learning opportunities. Students move from being the product of teaching to the center of learning. Many educators begin flipping their classrooms by utilizing these readily accessible resources. The videos and screencasts are available for students to view whenever and wherever they choose—whether at home, during study halls, on buses, or even in hospitals—allowing them to watch as many times as needed. This accessibility helps students come to class better prepared (Musallam, 2011). By leveraging students' preparation, teachers can spend more class time on integrating and applying knowledge through various student-centered, active learning strategies, such as conducting research or collaborating on projects with peer.

Additionally, teachers can use classroom time to assess each student's understanding and provide support as needed.

Some have argued that the student-centered instruction and engaged, active learning made possible in a flipped classroom represents what should already be occurring in classrooms (Stumpfenhorst, 2012).

Karen Cator, former director of the Office of Educational Technology for the U.S. Department of Education, also says that Flipped Learning may increase parents' participation in their students' learning. Cator acknowledges that while the trend toward Flipped Learning is growing, more research is required in order to determine its effectiveness (Baker, 2012).

These teachers believe that a flipped classroom sacrifices actual instruction in order to increase opportunities for student collaboration and activities generated and led by students. However,

as Marshall (2013) points out in her model of Flipped Learning, one key role for teachers is to “lead from behind.” In other words, the teacher engages in “observation, feedback, and assessment” during class and,

in the process, guides the learners' thinking, in the best spirit of the Socratic Method.

CONCLUSION

As discussed in this paper, there is a need for additional qualitative and quantitative research to determine how to fully maximize the potential of the Flipped Learning model. However, the current research clearly indicates that this model can help create a learner-centered classroom environment. It should be regarded as a transformative shift in teaching and learning processes. By flipping the traditional model, educators can promote a student-centered approach that enhances engagement, fosters deeper understanding, and develops essential skills, for the 21st century. Michael Gorman (2012) noted that a learner-centered educator would create classroom activities that are action-oriented, authentic, connected, collaborative, innovative, intellectually challenging, engaging, project-driven, inquiry-focused, and promote self-actualization. Gojak (2012) emphasized that the pertinent question is not whether to flip the classroom, but rather how educators can leverage the advantages of this model to enhance their teaching effectiveness and improve students' conceptual understanding and procedural fluency when necessary. The Flipped Learning model acts as a bridge to achieving a learner-centered classroom, fostering the deeper learning that educators aspire to achieve. (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

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